

Original Research Article

Drawing the Wound: A Self-Study of Visual Modeling and Continued Becoming an Elementary Mathematics Teacher Educator

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ABSTRACT: Each of the writers of this manuscript came to this work because of our past experiences as students, teachers, and as Mathematics Teacher Educators (MTEs). Loughran (2004), a self-study methodologist, describes research on teaching as inherently intertwined, noting that “as one alters so does the other, so the traditional notion of research whereby holding the problem in place while it is researched is not so straightforward in self-study” (p. 841). This fluidity reflects how self-study methodologies capture the evolving learning of the researcher. This manuscript is in a sense a methods paper, documenting our inquiry, but necessarily remains very personal, showing how our stories and emotions propelled the process of inquiry. In our dialogical collaborative inquiry, we began with a self-study approach that allowed us to closely examine our own teaching and decision-making in elementary math methods classes. As our questions developed, our methodology expanded to include quantitative data and qualitative case study methods. Guided by the rehumanizing mathematics perspective, we conceptualize elementary pre-service teachers’ struggles not simply as misconceptions or resistance, but as mathematical wounds,

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embodied, emotional, and historically situated injuries shaped by prior schooling, interpersonal messages, and structural features of mathematics education. In our research, we selected methodological tools progressively as we sought to surface and examine our hidden cognitions – the truths which shaped our individual pedagogies. Our goal was to make our private or hidden sense-making public by engaging ourselves, our students, and fellow MTEs in shared reflection on a problem of practice. This paper focuses on Karie’s evolving journey and understanding as we collaboratively worked to better understand elementary pre-service teachers’ (EPSTs’) struggles and how we might better support them. Throughout this iterative process, we made sense together while also incorporating insights from other MTEs, EPSTs, and existing research on result-oriented mathematics teacher education, as we attempted to “hold the problem in place.”

KEYWORDS: (re)humanizing mathematics, mathematics teacher educators, self-study, pre-service teachers, mathematics wounds

Here you may see the best portrait that, later, I was able to make of him. But my drawing is certainly very much less charming than its model. That, however, is not my fault. The grown-ups discouraged me in my painter's career when I was six years old, and I never learned to draw anything, except boas from the outside and boas from the inside.

– Antoine de Saint-Exupéry from *The Little Prince*

Teachers’ pedagogies are informed by their cognitive sets. Cognitive sets were theorized by Calhoun (1984) as a network of beliefs that are passively acquired, largely unarticulated, and “dark,” meaning hidden (p. 338). These sets direct our attention to patterns and associations for making meaning, are “pre-reflective” (p. 244), and are supplied by the one who is making meaning.

One cognitive set that repeatedly emerged in this inquiry comes from what I (Karie) believe to be true about my practice. Recalling my time as a new middle school math teacher, I found myself exploring agency in my classroom. I believe this stems from the lack of agency I felt as a child and even as an adult. In this collaborative self-study, we explored the ways I incorporated our collaborative research into practice. Within the realm of embodied knowledge research exists the study of emotional knowing. Furtak (2018) differentiates emotional knowing from the dispassionate cognition that is often insufficient for grasping some truths, arguing that our emotions are “epistemologically indispensable” (p. 576) in supporting whether and how we accept ideas as true. The ways this has manifested in me include the ongoing ways I conduct my classes, sometimes at great personal cost. I know the time I put into my course and my students may directly interfere with my professional goals vis-à-vis that carrot called tenure which is dangled precariously before us, yet supporting my students remains central to my values even if it is not central to hegemonic tenure rubrics. This emotional knowing is strong and unavoidable, like a rock in my shoe.

Academically, dark cognition refers to knowledge that is not immediately understood by the knower. Because of this, we structure this methodological paper by the phases of reframing in which we engaged throughout the study. Our primary goal was twofold: to honor the complexity of understanding built as we made sense of our decisions while teaching mathematics education content courses, and to synthesize barriers to engaging Elementary Pre-Service Teachers (EPSTs) in problem-based pedagogy and rigorous mathematics. In this journey, we began seeking to answer, “How are we working to rehumanize our mathematics methods and content courses for EPSTs?”

As we engaged in this work, we found ourselves returning repeatedly to the language of injury, residue, and repair. The beliefs we and our students carried were not merely incorrect or underdeveloped; they were often hurtful, lodged in the body and memory, and resistant to change through explanation alone. We came to describe these enduring imprints as mathematical wounds, a metaphor that allowed us to attend simultaneously to emotion, history, identity, and pedagogy. Although we do not fully unpack this concept until later in the paper, we introduce it here to orient the reader to the lens through which this self-study unfolds.

In the process of inquiry, our team rejected a linear discrete model of research in favor of a cyclical model that emphasizes collaborative, care-oriented inquiry situated within multiple communities and contexts. This cyclical model was depicted as a triangular pyramid with faces that directed the inquiry and a base centered on our problem of practice. To Karie, this depiction hearkens back to teaching middle school, a useful meta-reminder of how the events and the people in our lives continue to instruct our understandings and ways of making sense.

Literature Review

Self-based methodologies (SBM) have been a powerful tool for mathematics teacher educators to analyze and improve practice (Chapman et al., 2020); explore new theories and pedagogies (Kastberg et al., 2025); and bring their whole selves, histories, cultures, ways of thinking into their inquiries (Cox et al., 2014; Cox & D'Ambrosio, 2015; Grant & Butler, 2018; Kastberg et al., 2018, 2019). Self-study, as a form of SBM, has likewise been used to generate new knowledge about teaching and learning (LaBoskey, 2004). A key facet of self-study research is the need to provide convincing evidence (Hamilton & Pinnegar, 1998), and deliberate data that transparently allows for interpretations and claims. Foundational to the field is the belief that research on teaching should be carried out by teachers themselves (Loughran, 2004). Self-study is personal and builds on reflective practice to make new learning public. Generally, self-study draws on multiple aspects of quantitative and qualitative research as needed and is distinguished by the intentional blurring of the lines between the researcher and the research (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 2004), a stance that allows for emerging interpretations. Although initially marginalized within more positivistic academic traditions, self-study endured through the creative work of scholars committed to research grounded in teachers' epistemologies (Korthagen, 1995). Loughran argues that while self-study is meant to be responsive and that the challenge of "holding the problem in place" (Loughran, 2004, p 24) has long eluded self-study research. Recent work, such as Donaldson et al.'s exploration of enacting anti-racist pedagogies, demonstrates how self-study continues to evolve to address pressing problems of practice (Kastberg et al., 2025).

Collaboration is common across SBM, including autoethnography, scholarly personal narrative, and self-study. For instance, Vomvoridi-Ivanovic, van Ingen Lauer & Ward (2025) examined how their identities as mothers and mathematics teacher educators intersected, while scholarly personal narrative encourages researchers to bring their full selves, including emotions and interpretive lenses, into their work, embracing the "masks they present to the world" (Bradley & Nash, 2011, p. 18). In a scholarly personal narrative on the impacts of community college, Zamani-Gallaher et al. (2017) used collective storytelling to interrogate how, despite their later success as first-generation PhDs, they were labeled "unsuccessful" according to conventional community college metrics.

An emerging dimension of SBM, one particularly relevant to this study, is the use of imagery and artifacts as tools for making sense of experience. Pithouse-Morgan and colleagues argue that visual and material artifacts can serve as powerful mediators in collaborative inquiry, helping researchers surface tacit knowledge, reveal layered meanings, and communicate insights

that may remain inaccessible through language alone. Artifacts, including drawings, images, objects, and visual metaphors, offer alternative pathways for expressing personal, emotional, and embodied dimensions of teaching that are difficult to articulate (Pithouse-Morgan et al., 2012). In self-study research, such imagery not only deepens reflective engagement but also strengthens the trustworthiness of the work by making researchers' sense-making processes visible and shareable with others. Incorporating artifacts thus aligns with the broader commitments of SBM to transparency, relationality, and the honoring of multiple ways of knowing.

Process

Our process involved dialogical interaction among us as we considered multiple perspectives, our own, each other's, those of EPSTs, beginning teachers, and fellow MTEs – to deepen our understanding of students' experiences and how they feel about mathematics (Brown-Tess et al., 2022). The "text" in this study included: (a) the artifacts we created (drawings, written reflections, field notes), (b) the student work and survey responses, (c) our recorded conversations, and (d) the scholarly literature informing our analysis. We approached these overlapping texts through a recursive, interpretive cycle, engaging in iterative meaning-making as we sought to "hold the problem in place" while acknowledging that our understandings shifted with each interaction (Loughran, 2004). We aimed to synthesize insights into a coherent interpretation while maintaining a reflective stance and openness to critique.

By integrating these methods, we bring our whole selves, intellectual, emotional, and embodied, into the research, aligning with calls to re-humanize mathematics teacher education and mathematics education research. Through the multiple gazes of peer MTEs, EPSTs and beginning teachers, we gain critical perspectives that help to guard against self-justification, push us to interrogate our assumptions, focal points, and interpretations. Such collaborative scrutiny allowed our findings to be scrutinized and reread, increasing confidence that our experiences and interpretations could hold relevance beyond our unique and contextualized teaching experiences (Bodone et al., 2004; Loughran & Northfield, 1998), giving us our analytical framework for the rest of our work (see Skultety et al., 2023 for details).

Guiding Framework: (Re)humanizing Perspective

Our self-study group used a re(humanizing) perspective (Gutiérrez, 2018) to examine our practice with the aim of uncovering the unconscious frames from which we operate. This re(humanizing) perspective contains eight dimensions: (a) participation/positioning, (b) cultures/histories, (c) windows/mirrors, (d) living practice, (e) broadening math, (f) creation, (g) body/emotions, and (h) ownership. Although these dimensions attend specifically to mathematics teaching, we applied them methodologically as points of analytic attention, and tools for structuring in our collective reflections of our experiences within the self-study.

Initially we analyzed our own experiences as learners of mathematics and how these experiences shaped the ways we attempted to support EPSTs. With the re(humanizing) perspective, we aimed to critically attend to each of the dimensions in our engagement amongst ourselves, with the MTE community, and with EPSTs in our classes. Because our overarching aim was improved practice, this orientation permeated our questions, the methods through which we explored them, ways we sought to answer them, as well as our inquiry of practice.

The next sections focus on Karie's self-study, framed within the collaborative project. We then show how she utilized ongoing findings from the collaborative study to develop improvements for her course and what she learned in that process.

Context: Karie

I teach in an urban, accelerated certification master's program in which all candidates already hold bachelor's degrees in fields ranging from secondary teaching and literature to computer programming. Our students are truly diverse. The program is housed in a minority-serving institution, and candidates include recent college graduates, career changers, and even grandparents seeking to serve their communities as teachers. Many hold provisional licenses and are already the teacher of record in their classrooms, while others work as aides or teaching assistants. Several EPSTs teach in languages other than English, as local districts and charter schools offer elementary programs in Spanish, Chinese, French, and additional languages.

The program supports candidates by providing paid positions in local schools when they do not already have employment. Coursework is scheduled around teaching hours and district calendars. During the summer, students participate in an intensive introduction that includes classroom management and culturally sustaining pedagogies, followed by introductory coursework in language and reading and a two-credit hour mathematics class focused on problem-based pedagogy and number and operations content. This summer session launches their one-year program through in-person classes that help students build strong relationships with one another and with the faculty members and the supervisors who will mentor them throughout the year. This class is key in establishing the rehumanizing framework for the entire set of three courses students take for certification. The two-credit hour math course, like the other summer offerings, is an intensive five-day experience, meeting for six hours per day across two to three weeks.

The Generative Role of Imagery

This work took many forms across our inquiries, but for me (Karie) the process was always deeply visual. Throughout our collaboration I created multiple models to represent my thinking and to support conversations about how we were each conceptualizing the work, the nature of our findings, and our emerging perceptions. I consistently reconceptualized and re-represented data, literature, and methods in nontraditional ways. I can recall moments when collaborators felt frustrated after we had agreed on a model and I later returned with a revised version or questioned an idea we thought was settled. Yet this cycle of creating, disrupting, and rebuilding ultimately pushed our work and our shared understandings. In this sense, my use of imagery functioned as a generative mode of inquiry, offering space for interpretation and ongoing sense-making, much like the visual and arts-based practices described by Pithouse-Morgan and colleagues (Pithouse-Morgan & van Laren, 2012; Pithouse-Morgan et al., 2014).

I opened this paper with a quote from my favorite book, *The Little Prince*, because it reflects several themes central to this inquiry. The narrator frequently describes how a childhood experience discouraged him from drawing, yet he returns to drawing throughout the book, sometimes reluctantly, sometimes with frustration. His persistence, even as he experiences self-doubt, mirrors my own trajectory in school-based mathematics. Like the narrator, I experienced moments that dimmed my joy in creating and representing ideas, yet I had returned to these practices because they allow me to think, to question, and to see differently, aspects I learned in non-school settings. This interplay of vulnerability, persistence, and creative sense-making resonates strongly with my story and self-study literature, particularly with Pithouse-Morgan's (2012a, 2012b) attention to how personal histories and creative practices shape professional learning.

My relationship with drawing stretches back as far as I can remember, but I specifically learned to model in high school drafting courses. We were given machine components and asked to draw them from every angle so that someone unfamiliar with the object could build it. We learned how to represent hidden details with dotted lines and how to indicate movement within the constraints of two-dimensional space. That training profoundly shaped how I communicate, understand, and

interrogate ideas. Like the “drawing-as-dialogue” and “artful reflexivity” practices noted in Pithouse-Morgan’s work, these representational strategies became ways of thinking as much as ways of showing.

In this paper, I draw on those practices to represent the evolution of our inquiry as a three-dimensional pyramid rendered in two-dimensional form. My goal is to help readers see the nature and dynamics of our collaborative investigation. I also include some of the visual models I created for our research team. These images often served as catalysts for dialogue; they prompted us to challenge and extend each other’s perspectives, and I revised them repeatedly as our thinking shifted. Through this ongoing process, visual representation became both a method of inquiry and a means of making our developing understandings visible, an approach aligned with Pithouse-Morgan and van Laren (2015) framing of creative, relational, and representational practices as vital components of self-study methodology.

Fig. 1. Pyramid model of self-study where the base is our problem of practice.

Since we aimed to surface and interrogate our unconscious frames, we used collaborative self-study to make sense of our practice. We began with a dialogical approach, recognizing that while self-study is both individual and collective (Griffiths et al., 2004), intentional dialogue strengthens reframing and deepens inquiry. Through sustained conversation, we interpreted our individual experiences with one another, asked questions, pushed for clarity, and re-examined assumptions in real time. Our recorded dialogues therefore served simultaneously as data and analysis, evolving responsively as our inquiry unfolded.

Our collaborative inquiry unfolded in several phases, which we conceptualized as a four-sided triangular pyramid anchored in its base by our shared problem of practice (depicted as the black triangle in *Figure 1*). This problem of practice centered on our persistent struggle to influence EPSTs’ beliefs in our mathematics pedagogy courses. These beliefs, often shaped by narrow or restrictive views of mathematics, affected how EPSTs engaged with problem-based pedagogy and rigorous mathematical activity.

Phase 1. Phase 1 (Triangle 1 in *Figure 1*) focused on systematically investigating our initial problem of practice (Skultety et al., 2023). During this phase, we engaged in dialogical collaborative self-study, to examine our teaching practices, drawing upon our combined experiences as learners of mathematics, former classroom teachers, and MTEs.

Phase 2. To expand our understanding, we next brought our emerging framework to the Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators (AMTE) annual conference. There, we invited

other MTEs to discuss how they address EPSTs' restrictive views of mathematics and recorded the pedagogical tools and strategies shared by the broader community. Phase 2 (Triangle 2 in *Figure 1*) involved incorporating this community knowledge. As we refined the framework, we found it effectively captured several of the common implicit goals held by MTEs. This recognition prompted us to return to the literature with the framework in mind. In doing so, we identified multiple research-based surveys on mathematics teacher beliefs that attended to the same types of “wounds” we had named. During this phase, we also clarified our problem of practice. Drawing on insights from math teacher education research, we revisited our conceptions of the framework and re-engage with Phase 1 processes by reframing our interpretations using stories and more recent events in our classrooms as additional data sources.

Phase 3. With the new insights garnered through expanding our collaboration to the MTE community, we operationalized the model by designing a plan to compare the framework with EPST and beginning teacher perceptions through surveys and structured discussions. We identified three categories of practice central to addressing teacher beliefs and then collected data through surveys, written reflections, and course assignments tied to classroom practice. As we analyzed these materials, the complexity of EPSTs' interpretations became increasingly visible. Our collaborative team met three times to examine how students understood the survey items, how they responded to our pedagogical moves, and how their engagement revealed shifts, or resistance, in their responses. These analytic meetings/discussions served as cycles of reflection and interpretation, allowing us to refine both the framework and our understanding of how EPSTs negotiate their evolving view of mathematics learning and teaching.

Envisioning our process of self-study as a pyramid, allowed us to represent how our inquiry remained grounded in the shared problem of practice while still allowing movement across in our exploration. Just as one turns a three-dimensional object to examine its different faces, we shifted among the sides of the pyramid through our collaborative phases to examine the problem from different points of view. Each round of analysis led us to reframe the problem of practice and begin, revisit, or reengage peripheral collaborations represented in the faces of the pyramid. Conceptualizing our process as movement around the metaphor of a pyramid emphasizes that our inquiry was always grounded in the same foundational problem, yet we could shift perspectives. Through the modeling of our process in discussion, we planned to be continuously affected in our research and our outcome, so that our inquiries could shift as our perspectives shifted. As I wanted to be planning for responsive inquiry, I made other models, consistently nonlinear.

Phase 1: Reframing Through Collaborative Dialogical Self-Study

Our collaboration began with a phone call in which Stephanie invited us to explore a shared challenge in our teaching. Through our early conversations, we identified a common problem of practice: the limiting views many EPSTs held about mathematics, which directly influenced their engagement in our mathematics methods and content courses. Having taught these courses together at the same institution in the past, we shared a foundation that allowed us to collectively sharpen our practice across our new institutional contexts. To initiate our inquiry into these limiting views, we each developed and shared our “case stories” (Barksdale-Ladd et al., 2001; Korthagen & Lunenberg, 2004). We met virtually every two weeks on Zoom, exchanging experiences, stories, classroom artifacts, evaluations, and student emails. At this stage, dialogue was our primary tool. Through conversation, we collaboratively examined our past and present selves, as K–12 learners, as EPSTs, and as MTEs, and how these histories shaped our pedagogical choices.

My own problem of practice centered on the persistent disconnect between the pedagogies taught in my courses and the instructional decisions I saw PSTs enact in their field placements.

Each semester, I encountered statements or teaching artifacts that seemed to reject the principles of problem-based mathematics teaching. One particularly powerful moment occurred when I visited a former student's classroom. Sitting with her students at lunch, I watched the students work through a thick packet of low-cognitive demand worksheets, tasks devoid of conceptual grounding or problem-based thinking. Knowing she had been a strong math student in my course, I felt a profound sense of disappointment, even failure. This moment echoed the larger challenge documented in research: the difficulty MTE face when attempting to support EPSTs to implement problem-based approaches in real classrooms (Ernest, 1989; Franke, Kazemi, & Battey, 2007; Fennema et al., 1996; Raymond, 1997.) For me, this challenge is deeply personal.

I grew up in extreme poverty, where electricity and water were frequently shut off, and evenings often involved hauling water from neighbors, heating it on the stove, and preparing baths for our family of seven in a cramped, noisy trailer. Quiet space to study was nonexistent. On top of this, I struggled with reading and had weak short-term memory. And yet, I loved mathematics. I took only the classes necessary for graduation because I was working multiple jobs, but I completed every math class available. Like many students, I did not experience problem-based learning; mathematics was presented as repeated practice of modeled procedures. Although I struggled to memorize algorithms, many concepts felt intuitive. Each member of the collaboration brought similarly powerful stories that shaped the teaching we each strive to enact. We came to understand many of our experiences not simply as formative memories, but as mathematical wounds, experiences that still ache, still shape how we teach, and still surface in moments of doubt, urgency, and care. In what follows, we return to these wounds more explicitly, tracing how they specifically informed my pedagogical decisions and the collaborative framework that emerged from our self-study

These early conversations constituted a process of (re)humanizing ourselves as MTEs, aligned with Gutiérrez's (2018) (re)humanizing mathematics practices, particularly practices 2 and 7. We intentionally interpreted our experiences through our cultures and histories (practice 2) and made our emotional and intellectual framings transparent within our research community (practice 7). Our private emotions, often muted in academic spaces, became central analytic tools.

During this phase, we also shared the pedagogical strategies we used to address EPSTs' beliefs about mathematics. In my own courses, I began with mathematics journey maps (see *Figure 2*), used lesson study in partnership with local teachers to engage EPSTs in authentic problem-based methods, and assigned weekly mathematical problem sets drawing on content outside typical K–12 curricula (e.g., set theory, knot theory) to broaden EPSTs' conceptions of what counts as mathematics. As we aimed to attend to students' wounds, we must be clear that we do not condone using mathematical wounds as deficits to be fixed, but instead as historically and structurally produced responses to schooling. They become visible through language, pedagogical decisions, affective reactions, and resistance or compliance in mathematics learning environments.

As we analyzed the language we used to describe our goals and our efforts to address EPSTs' beliefs, it became clear that our practices were deeply emotional (Skultety et al., 2023). Lisa described her work as akin to being a counselor, and all of us used words such as care and love, terms that are not typically foregrounded in mathematics education literature, despite their presence in the work of scholars such as Noddings (1984) and Hackenberg (2010). The centrality of emotion in our reflections aligns with prior self-study literature (Kelchtermans & Hamilton, 2004). Through these emotionally charged discussions, the term "mathematical wounds" emerged to describe the barriers and injuries, historical, interpersonal, and structural, that shape EPSTs' relationships with mathematics.

Fig. 2. An artifact from the math journey exercise.

We connected these wounds to our own experiences of being othered or discouraged from fully engaging as “mathy” people. In my case, I vividly remember internalizing gendered messages suggesting mathematics was “for boys” or “for smart people,” even though, within my family, I was frequently considered smart. My difficulty with memorization was a source of shame, reinforced by comments from family and teachers. In geometry, when I could not recall theorems and postulates, I created my own based on what made sense, all the while believing I was cheating. Others in our group shared experiences where gender, race, language, or class positioned them as outsiders to mathematics. We also described injuries produced not only by interpersonal messages but by the structure of school mathematics itself, which often hides the broader, creative, and joyful dimensions of the discipline.

These individual narratives, combined with stories of colleagues, loved ones, and students, illuminated the intergenerational and systemic nature of these mathematical wounds. Collectively, we were all striving, implicitly and explicitly, to create healing in our classrooms.

We began our work by establishing a shared vocabulary. During a powerful collaborative conversation focused on our students' histories and pedagogical struggles, the phrase “mathematical wounds” emerged to capture the profound impact of past experiences on preservice teachers' learning. We sat with this metaphor and developed our notion of what meanings it entailed – the lingering injuries people carry from their encounters with mathematics, moments of shame, exclusion, silencing, or misrecognition that become lodged in the body and resurface as fear, avoidance, overcompliance, or control. Like physical wounds, they may scar rather than disappear, restricting movement even as individuals continue to function. From this initial collaboration, we developed the Mathematical Wounds Framework, which categorizes the three wounds we sought to address and identifies three general approaches for supporting mathematical healing (see Skultety et al., 2023 for the full framework and its development).

Phase 2: “Reframing” the Frame, Expanding the Collaboration, and “Making Public”

In Phase 2, we broadened our collaborative sphere to include the wider mathematics teacher education (MTE) community. Our goal was twofold: (a) to deepen our theoretical grounding, and (b) to make our work public so that others could interrogate, refine, or extend our early

conceptualizations. Although we had previously reviewed the MTE literature, once the concept of mathematical wounds emerged in Phase 1, we recognized the need to revisit the literature with new questions. We sought to understand in what ways MTEs have already attended to the injuries, barriers, and histories EPSTs bring into mathematics, and how those existing practices aligned with the three core categories and healing approaches defined in the Mathematical Wounds Framework (Skultety et al., 2023). This re-examination helped us honor ongoing work in the field and clarify how our framework intersected with and extended existing approaches to reduce barriers EPSTs experience when learning and teaching mathematics.

To further extend our dialogical inquiry, in Spring 2022 we presented our emerging framework at the Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators (AMTE) annual conference. Our session, *Purposefully Addressing Preservice Teachers' Mathematics Wounds in Elementary Education Programs*, invited MTEs to engage with and critique the framework. We began the session by asking participants to reflect on two questions: 1. What mathematical wounds do you see EPSTs bring into your courses? And 2. In your own courses, have you intentionally addressed your or your EPSTs' mathematical wounds? If so, how?

After this individual reflection, we introduced the three categories of mathematical wounds from our framework (Skultety et al., 2023). Participants then worked in small groups to identify activities, tasks, or experiences they used in their own courses that aligned with a specific wound and discuss how these practices supported EPSTs in recognizing, naming, or beginning to heal that wound. Participants recorded their group's thinking in a shared Google document. Their contributions revealed that the wounds framework provided a powerful language for describing and analyzing their pedagogical decisions. For instance, one MTE described designing tasks that "press wounds" to move toward healing, while another described activities that validated wounds before introducing research to support "wound-breaking."

Across groups, MTEs reported the term "wounds" helped them articulate goals and assumptions underlying their teaching practices, goals that had previously been implicit or unspoken. In this way, the framework helped make their work more visible, more communal, and more theoretically grounded. This phase ultimately led us to reframe our problem of practice from its original focus on EPSTs' limiting views to a broader and more generative question: How are we, as MTEs, working to (re)humanize our mathematics methods and content courses so that EPSTs can, in turn, take up the work of (re)humanizing mathematics in their own classrooms?

Return to phase 1: Reframe Collaborative Dialogical Self-Study

We returned to our smaller dialogical collaborative self-study team invigorated by the ways other MTEs were taking up the language of mathematical wounds. We found that wound 1 (Beliefs about Teaching Mathematics) and wound 3 (Beliefs about Self as a Doer and Teacher of Mathematics) heavily recurred and were addressed in MTE examples, including ours. Wound 2 (Beliefs About Mathematics Teaching and Learning) was addressed about half as much. This finding was interesting in that our goal in this self-study was to specifically address limiting beliefs that impacted engagement in the course, and later practice. This led us to question and consider whether beliefs about ourselves as a math teacher was another unique wound. We ended up keeping it nested within teachers' beliefs about themselves as mathematicians.

Processing the community discussion from the AMTE conference in our smaller collaborative team, we discussed what information we might need from our own EPSTs to understand how to address their math wounds. This marked the beginning of our work on developing a validated survey that would enable us and others to identify EPSTs' math wounds. Returning to the literature bases identified in phases 1 and 2, we analyzed published studies that contained validated surveys about EPSTs' beliefs and collaboratively organized questions from these validated surveys and

aligned them with each of the three math wounds nested within our math wounds framework. To accomplish this, we created a shared google document and collaboratively filled out a graphic organizer. We worked in pairs (Stephanie/Juan, Neet Priya/Lisa, Karie/Adam) and lifted validated survey questions from each study and recorded the specific question, source from which the question came, and the wound(s) we perceived the question aligned with. This process led to the identification of nearly 40-60 validated survey questions that aligned with each of the three math wounds, nearly 160 questions in total. *Figure 3* provides a small snapshot of the survey items and how we collaborated to select items which matched our objectives.

Item	Rankings	Wound	specified wound?	shift/change in PSTs?	different responses	honest	ambiguity?	Total
Mathematics makes me feel inadequate.		Wound 1	3	3	2	1	3	12
I am not the type of person who is good at mathematics.	3	Wound 1	3	2	2	2	3	12
I think I am good at mathematics.		Wound 1	3	3	2	1	3	12
I am confident in my ability to solve difficult mathematics problems.	4	Wound 1	3	3	2	3	3	14
I enjoy learning about mathematics.	5	Wound 1	3	2	2	1	3	11
I tend to not ask questions in math classes because I am afraid I will look dumb.	6	Wound 1	3	2	2	3	3	13
I get frustrated when I do mathematics.		Wound 1	3	2	2	3	3	13
Overall, I feel confident in my mathematical ability.		Wound 1	3	2	2	2	3	12
When a math problem arises that I can't immediately solve, I stick with it until I have the solution	7	Wound 1	3	3	2	1	3	12

Fig. 3. Sample of spreadsheet used to make sense of mathematical wounds through literature.

Next, we aimed to narrow down the list of questions for each math wound to 10-15 questions, for a total of 30-45 questions that would ultimately comprise our survey. To achieve this goal, we separated into pairs and evaluated each survey item by the following questions: (a) To what extent does this question align with the specified wound?, (b) To what extent could this question measure a shift/change in EPSTs?, (c) To what extent will this elicit different responses from EPSTs?, (d) To what extent will this question elicit an honest response from EPSTs?, and (e) To what extent is this question clear and does it limit potential ambiguity? Questions were ranked from 1 to 10 or 15, and likelihood to address the questions above was rated using the following Likert scale: (a) 3 = perfect, (b) 2 = so-so, and (c) 1 = not at all. Ultimately, the group met to compare their assigned scores and agree on a final list of 10-15 survey questions for each math wound. We incorporated the revised survey within three classrooms with EPSTs who had finished their mathematics methods courses on teaching through problem solving. While we were confident, we had a strong tool for providing a snapshot of the mathematical wounds our EPSTs carried, we saw a need for including student voices to make their invisible interpretation of these questions visible as well as in some way help us cross-validate the self-reported surveys. This took place in Stage 4.

In collaborative self-study meetings, we independently identified each of the factors with our descriptions of the three wounds. We then came together and discussed how we understood the connections. I continued to struggle by listing beliefs about oneself as a doer of mathematics and oneself as a teacher of math in a single category. Most of the factors did not fit cleanly in one wound, see *Figure 4*. While both incorporated beliefs about mathematics, factor 2 dealt more with mathematics teacher identity while wound 4 could isolate the EPST identity as a mathematician, apart from teaching. The exploration of the factors continued to show me that they could be separate wounds. I organized the following model (*Figure 4*) to communicate with the group how the factors demonstrated something unique about the two parts of wound 2. I am not sure where

Fig. 4. *The mathematical wounds and the survey questions.*

this struggle originated, but in part I think it was tangential to Ball's writing on PKT. There she isolated teacher knowledge about mathematics and mathematics teaching as distinct categories. My experience working with students who were more confident in their math, having more success in traditional education structures, did not demonstrate a lack of wounds. Like the story I told of my student who as a teacher was providing an experience of math learning absent of building conceptual knowledge. She was the most confident math student in my class. I couldn't get over the feeling that we would be missing something important by bundling these wounds. In our discussion, we decided to keep the 3-wound structure, because the factors did provide a unique angle for analyzing the wound in both parts.

Stage 3: Expansion/ Listening / Voices / Students

For the fourth phase, we re-engaged with the (re)humanizing mathematics perspective. We were critical of whose knowledge we were incorporating in our collaborations and specifically wanted to position EPSTs' interpretations of the problem of practice and pedagogical moves for addressing the problem of practice. In my class, we analyzed EPST responses to the survey with the EPSTs. This took place in a class of master's students seeking elementary teaching certification. I didn't tell the EPSTs about the problem of practice or the wounds framework. I wanted to get their interpretations without accidentally communicating that there were "right answers." The importance of linking self-study to students' thinking is common in self-based research, including early self-study documents (Barnes, D., 1998; Zeichner, 1999). Like other self-study research, we wanted to position students as contributors who are shaping and responding to the study, (similar to Freese, 1998; Hutchinson, N. L. et al., 1996; Trumbull & Cobb, 2000). Like Russell and Bullock (1999), we believed that "without a sustained and thoughtful study of [our] practice and [our] students' learning, we would only be interpreting, or assuming, that what we were attempting to

portray was being apprehended by our students” (Loughran, 2004, p. 22). In our case, we were looking at our practice and wanted to know if EPSTs recognized the wounds in any form and if they felt the pedagogical moves made in their math classes supported them. For this phase, we needed to understand how EPSTs interpreted survey questions. We sought to answer, “As MTEs, how are our efforts to rehumanize mathematics methods and content courses being interpreted by EPSTs?”

We intentionally involved students by leading a class discussion on the revised survey results. In Summer 2022, I administered the updated survey in one section of our elementary methods course and then shared that class’s aggregated results (see *Figure 5*). Our goals were to check whether students interpreted the questions as we intended and to identify any variation in their interpretations. These EPST were in their first course of an elementary certification program, and the discussion revealed that several survey items were understood differently by the new EPSTs than by our research team, and differently from one another. We selected nine questions that showed notable variation, clear splits in beliefs, or otherwise unexpected results. For example, the item “Math teachers should show students the exact way to answer every question they will be tested on” was designed to probe beliefs about students’ ability to solve problems creatively. However, some students interpreted it instead as a question about fairness in testing students on unfamiliar material. Insights from this discussion led us to revise or remove several survey items.

Fig. 5. Sharing survey results that were confusing – example of a slide used in class discussion.

As we explored survey responses, I began mapping responses of students in radials (See *Figure 6*), which provided snapshots of potential wounds communicated through the survey, allowing us to see shifts in the class or in a student from the pre-program survey to the post-program survey. As I showed these radials to the team, some expressed concern that we could be simplifying our students and their experiences. Our team debated the use of a radial or any simple image to represent the complexity of experiences or beliefs of our students. For me, I did not intend to flatten my students in that way, but something about the radials felt like it was expanding the ways I could see them. Of course, I know that surveys inherently flatten data and people. Or in our case, a novice to mathematics education vernacular may rank their confidence in teaching math as very high, but as they grow, they learn that learning is complicated, personal, and situated. They may then lower their confidence ranking. With a simplified view, we may say they regressed, but with some understanding, we could see that ranking confidence more carefully might demonstrate less woundedness because they represent the teaching of mathematics more accurately. We found

Fig. 6. Radial of a group of students² presented at AMTE 2024

agreement that the radials were like a picture, a snapshot of a day. And like any picture, there is a lot that is not represented (like smell or voice) and a lot can be misrepresented (weird shadows or light creating an illusion.) That being said, comparing the snapshot could still tell us something that could extend beyond the day or captured image. We committed ourselves and future interpretations to scrutinize findings from the radial to truly and faithfully use the rehumanizing framework for the study.

Using the radials to examine both wounds and factors, we observed that students' categorized beliefs were often, but not always, interconnected. In *Figure 6*, for instance, Student C was the only participant who consistently scored a 5 (indicating the highest woundedness). All other students, even those with relatively healthy profiles, showed some wounded beliefs within particular categories. For example, Student B demonstrated strong perseverance in doing mathematics but rated their confidence as a 4, indicating they felt wounded when encountering unfamiliar problems.

With revised surveys, new tools for analyzing EPST's mathematical wounds, and years of collaborative sense making, I embarked on the first cohort where I applied the wounds framework.

Here we go, our first round of applying lessons learned.

When we began this work, we were already addressing wounds, though we did not call it that. Through our self-study, we listed our efforts to support students healing of traumatic experiences

² The survey used a 5-point Likert scale, but the meaning of "5" varied across items, on some questions it indicated woundedness, while on others it indicated healthy perspectives. To make the results comparable, we recorded the data so that a score of 5 always represented the highest level of woundedness. As a result, the radial chart displays these translated scores rather than the original survey responses.

associated with mathematics and shared our own experience which spurred the work we were doing. We were unpacking EPST's experiences in the mathematics classroom, we engaged in doing math with EPSTs, and we supported EPSTs in enacting high-quality teaching practices. Now with the survey, we were specifically asking the students before and after the collective math coursework for the certification program, how they felt about themselves doing and teaching math, the nature of mathematics, and beliefs about how to teach and how students learn to do mathematics. At the end of the program, students described courses as "life-changing" and "inspiring." Even my most anxious student, in tears, expressed regret that her K-12 experience was so different from what she was learning to do and wondered how things would have changed for her if she had the experiences she was designing for her students. The course was structured to demonstrate and provided opportunities for the EPSTs to try on problem-based learning as well as experience and co-create rigorous challenging and rewarding math problems with their students. EPSTs practice implementing high quality routines and share them with one another and give feedback to one another on how to improve. I had specifically created a system for tracking that data, and now coding their interpretations, feedback and support by the wounds I was analyzing.

And like years past, I was again surprised by specific comments PST had made. One of the two strongest students in their final presentation of teaching, expressed that students must memorize their facts before they could do interesting problems. I was surprised that she still had this belief when we specifically addressed how students build fact fluency. There was even a moving moment in that class where our most anxious EPST explained in class how transformational the discussion was and how she wished she had this experience as a child. Even still, this student still believed that lack of facts inhibited working memory. While learning facts is the goal in elementary math classes, when teachers believe that not knowing facts prevents students from being able to engage with problems conceptually and develop lessons based on this belief, they restrict the learning of students (Kamii & Dominick 1998; Narode et al., 1993). This belief hits home for me. I would have been that child, and I was that child, denied rich learning opportunities connected to the math I was learning. In my soul, I believe denying children the chance to solve worthwhile problems is a specific violence. How did a student who spent a year in my class still hold this view? I also saw PSTs use and recommend "tricks" for solving math problems in lieu of building conceptual understanding. My feelings of failure rushed back. What changed with all this labor to understand and creation and recreation to heal? This revealed some inconsistencies in my thinking about learning. Despite my strong drive to create agentic classrooms, I did not explore how my students had their own cognitions and dark cognitions that drove what they would even pay attention to. Like me, they would not learn by just being told or shown a thing, but as a sort of reaction to some deeply seeded cognition they held.

The initial concern, raised months ago with collaborators about whether the radials would inhibit student expression, was challenged by the survey results. The radials ultimately shifted my understanding of progress away from just the 2-3 end-of-course student statements to a web of beliefs. The survey results clearly showed growth in specific, measurable beliefs and demonstrated how student learning connected to EPSTs overall system of beliefs. The funny thing about not tracking the beliefs is that for years, all my attention went to the comments from students in the class, specifically my attention clung to comments that demonstrated a continued wounded perspective. In truth, my student had a map of wounds far more complex than those few comments. While in a moment they might express a changed perspective or life change, they might also express deeply held beliefs that deny their students high quality mathematics learning. Obviously, my PSTs are as complicated as us MTE's who specifically investigated our dark knowledge manifested in our feelings and our practices at the start of this project. We can only

change so much, and my limited attention narrowed all EPST learning to vocal students making very particular comments rather than a holistic assessment of the web of wounds and health and healing making up each EPST. I can only impact so much for our students. They can only know so much about themselves as well. And so, I learned in this pilot study, that the learning of my previous classes were likely just as complicated and I had not been adequately assessing their learning or my progress in supporting them. This reinvigorated my energy to use the survey and radials to help me understand my students.

I integrated this learning into my course, beginning with the first iteration of the study in Summer 2024. My primary pedagogical move was to progressively increase the collaborative nature of assignments across both the 2024 and 2025 iterations. My aim was to decenter myself as the primary evaluator to create a non-performative space where EPSTs could meaningfully support one another in doing mathematics, sharing their experiences, and engaging in sensemaking. While this shift was intended to foster shared success, the adjustment was particularly challenging during the peer problem-solving activities. Group work often led to scenarios where some students avoided engaging with the mathematics: either by a "strong math person" attempting to "save" anxious peers from thinking, or by the more anxious EPST simply checking out. Despite these group dynamics challenges, I consistently incorporated lesson study in partnering classrooms to provide a dedicated, low-stakes lab for trying out problem-based pedagogy.

My core pedagogical goal is to continuously direct EPSTs' attention to children's mathematical thinking and learning from that thinking. Our program begins with an intense, 2-credit hour summer course focused on problem-based learning and the content/pedagogy of numbers and operations. Due to shifts I made responding to EPSTs' explicit thinking in the course, the structure has evolved significantly from its original 5-day, 6-hour on-campus format. The current iteration is highly blended, designed to integrate theory with practice: 1. The original 5-day week is now delivered through a rotation of different settings: 2 days on campus; 2 partial days at a local non-profit summer school; 2 partial days dedicated to Professional Learning Communities (PLCs); 2 partial days in synchronous online class sessions; and a final day completed asynchronously. 2. To establish a focus on student thinking immediately, I provide a video of my instruction where the camera focuses exclusively on children using thinking strategies. 3. In partnership with the summer school, EPSTs tutor assigned classes, collecting data on student understanding of a specific assigned topic. 4. The third day of class is dedicated to a hands-on "Numbers and Operations Activity Expo" (See *Figure 7*).

In the subsequent course, each student submits a video of their teaching in a modified lesson study structure. Students report learning a lot from watching each other's teaching. Over the course of the year, I see the quality of their questions and feedback improving. While they always celebrate each other, they become resources for each other, and their questions become more poignant. Finally, in the last course, they deeply study the thinking of a small group of students, plan a lesson on their learning, and then re-interview those students to analyze what learning was accomplished. They present this work in their PLC groups. Overall, I see the EPSTs begin to trust their students. They begin giving challenging problems-based lessons or try out high quality routines, because they see other teachers trying it. However, despite this, when an EPST's attempt at implementing a PBL lesson does not go well, peers respond in different ways. While some peers recommend "telling kids how to do it first," others suggest more supportive structures that could support a PBL lesson, such as classroom management ideas or talk moves. In the PLC feedback, EPST's beliefs are made explicit through interpretation and advice. The community can then address the very real barriers to teaching. Some teachers demonstrated a shift in their trust of their students over the course of the year, evidenced in their feedback.

Fig. 7. EPSTs³ working through an Operations Activity Expo and EPSTs collecting data on student understanding

I am now in the middle of the second iteration, inundated with rich data about the EPST in the program. While the survey expanded my thinking of EPST beliefs, and taught me to trust EPSTs more, I still find myself telling them some things explicitly, beyond sharing research and strategies well established in the field, which could tend to more explicit instruction. I also learned they need to know my aims in the activities, homework and design of the course, beyond course goals and essential questions. In the first iteration, there was a continued complaint about doing math that they would never teach. So, we committed a class to understanding the mathematical horizon and how all elementary teachers, besides being resourced for teaching any grade they are certified to teach, must understand the mathematical horizon (the sunrise and sunset) to best support their students. By making space in the class to specifically and directly address conflicts that surfaced.

³ Images have been altered to protect the identities of students.

Discussion

By weaving through qualitative and quantitative research, we allowed the methods to speak to, expand, translate, guide and challenge previous findings, our research and ourselves as MTEs. This project was intentionally driven by our emotions and our whole selves as legitimate tools of triangulation and iteratively and creatively implemented the feelings and intuitions of others outside of our group to also test, challenge and interpret findings as they emerged. Currently, our team is in the second iteration of the final survey to be given to EPSTs in certification programs. While we continue to engage in cycles of collaborative meaning making in this ongoing self-study, we reject the idea that there is one truth. Instead, we continue to aim for complicated sense-making in the communities to which we belong. In subsequent cycles, for me, the models I create are helpful tools for seeing, communicating, and collaborating.

While I am giving over the learning more to the community of EPSTs, and analyzing the ways they are making progress, learning from each other and from their students, I still see in myself the exercising of more traditional practices. Specifically, I struggle trusting my student to engage in the math we do in the course. So much so that when I saw a student allowing his group to do the math without him, I explicitly said that there will be a final in the end, so everyone will need to make sure they know the material. That student did come to me and try the problem again, so I produced the immediate behavior I wanted to see, but I felt and still feel uneasy relying on these sorts of structures. Similarly, I have seen an uptick in the use of AI to solve math problems. I still don't know how to support PSTs to be brave in engaging in difficult mathematics. The thing about wounds is that they hurt. They produce such powerful fear reactions. Like my teenage self, who sought to hide my struggle with memory for fear and shame, my EPSTs have their own powerful forces. Accountability measures feel superficial and don't really produce the healing I seek to affect, but I don't know what does. How did I heal? Honestly, I still am anxious about my memory. This wound created a scar that might always restrict some movement. Isn't that what wounds do?

Fig. 8. Pyramid model of self-study viewed from above

Again, imagine the pyramid from *Figure 1*, but viewed from the top as shown in *Figure 8*. While we began this project and moved from phase 1 to phase 3, future iterations will likely move across phases, specifically re-engaging with phase 3 repeatedly to better our understanding the impact of pedagogical practices on the mathematical wounds EPSTs experience. By viewing the model from the top of the pyramid, we see a model of self-study that plans for the inclusion of others in the self-study as needed.

In phase 1, we began our collaborative self-study. In phase 2, we sought the understandings of other MTEs and researchers regarding the finding that emerged from our first phase. We then returned to phase 1 to intentionally integrate perspectives from others into our group's dialogical, collaborative self-study. In phase 4, we sought yet another set of "others" – our EPSTs, whose input further informed our understanding.

Using this model, I am planning for future engagement with my cognitions, known and unknown. This pyramid represents community, those with me such as my students, colleagues, as well as the communities of the past who still impact me, like past students and teachers and my family, as well as the community I haven't met. I engage in conversation again and again, seeking to be truer to myself and to learn to provide space so others can likewise be growing in their communities.

My friends, like myself, have been skirting this danger for a long time, without ever knowing it; and so it is for them that I have worked so hard over this drawing. The lesson which I pass on by this means is worth all the trouble it has cost me.

– Antoine de Saint-Exupéry from *The Little Prince*.

Afterword: Dialogue Between Scholars

Our collaborative journey began with a shared question among our team of mathematics teacher educators: How are we working to rehumanize our mathematics methods and content courses for EPSTs? Initially, this question led us to chronicle our early collaborative history: how we identified a common problem of practice, and how that early connection grew into regular meetings where we exchanged literature, examined our teaching moves, and created a survey. Our first attempt to publish this work was unsuccessful, but the feedback received was instrumental. We began a process of "splicing" the manuscript, struggling to retain the narrative of our intellectual journey while conforming to traditional reporting structures. This internal tension manifested as a struggle to communicate the relationship between our qualitative, collaborative analysis and our quantitative efforts. We felt that the journey itself had taught us something important. Specifically, the way we moved from qualitative and quantitative ways of analyzing our teaching guided by the rehumanizing mathematics framework. Juan recommended the Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education.

Our core uncertainty about the paper's purpose persisted. Our critical friend and reviewer, Elizabeth, helped us confront this lack of clarity through incisive questions that forced us to articulate the paper's boundaries. Specifically, she challenged us on whether we were conducting a self-study, developing a survey instrument, or seeking to productively understand the complexity of our own work. Elizabeth's questions helped us recognize that centering the survey artifact distracted from the very relational framework and lived decisions we were trying to articulate. In conversations, she encouraged us to "put more of yourself in the manuscript," advocating for a clearer presence of our voices and experiences. Her guidance led us away from a traditional reporting outline, affirming that the survey development was important only as a part of the story of our self-study's "dance," not as the main finding.

In conversations with Elizabeth, we shared two possible directions the manuscript might take: a more traditional "New Self-Study Outline", and a second path that centered the survey's co-creation. Her questions helped us see that the survey, as an artifact, did not constitute a self-study, nor did it honor the journal's commitment to relational inquiry. Instead, it distracted from the very framework we were trying to articulate and the lived, sometimes personal conversations and decisions we made that led us to that framing. Elizabeth's constant encouragement was to "put

more of yourself in the manuscript.” This took up much of our dialogue as we struggled to do this. Much of our discovery around the survey remains, as a part of the story of the dance.

The current version of this manuscript is a direct result of attending to Elizabeth’s recommendations. It now reflects our commitment to prioritizing the narrative of how our self-study progressed and what it revealed, rather than attempting to report on every facet of our inquiry. We returned to the organic, often personal conversations from which our language around "wounds," productive struggle, and rehumanizing practices emerged. We agreed that instead of presenting generic examples for each wound, we would include specific, illustrative glimpses of ourselves and our practice. Ultimately, this final paper reflects a commitment to the relational, dialogue-driven nature of self-study, focusing on how our inquiry led us to a sustained and complex understanding of our problem of practice: How are we, as MTEs, working to rehumanize our mathematics methods and content courses for EPSTs?

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